

Original

Bibliometric analysis of scientific production on post-prostatectomy physical therapy indexed in Web of Science (2015–2024)

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Abstract

Physical therapy may contribute to the recovery of erectile function and urinary continence following surgical treatment for prostate cancer. The objective of this study was to determine the international trend in scientific output on physical therapy in prostatectomy. Records were retrieved from the Web of Science (2015–2024). Bibliometrix/RStudio software was used for the analysis. Production, authorship, countries, journals, and citations were analysed, and network maps were generated. A total of 228 publications were identified. The growth of the scientific literature was fitted to an exponential model with a coefficient of determination of 0.37. The author with the highest contribution was P.W. Hodges (8 articles; 184 citations). The world leader was the United States (46 papers; 827 citations). *Neurourology and Urodynamics* was the most productive journal (20 documents; 327 citations). The main research theme was pelvic floor recuperation in post-prostatectomy erectile dysfunction. The findings show that the volume of research in this area remains limited and suggest the need to strengthen specialist involvement and inter-institutional collaboration. These efforts are essential for consolidating knowledge and advancing the scientific impact of physical therapy in post-prostatectomy care.

Keywords: physical therapy; prostate cancer; prostatectomy; bibliometric analysis.

1. Introduction

Prostate cancer is one of the most common malignancies in men and a leading cause of cancer-related mortality. In 2020, prostate cancer accounted for approximately 21% of newly diagnosed cancer cases and 10% of all oncologic pathology-related deaths, underlining its significant impact on global cancer indicators [1].

Radical prostatectomy is currently the main line of treatment for patients with prostate cancer. Despite important advances in prostatectomy techniques, urinary incontinence and sexual dysfunction remain among the most frequent postoperative complications. [2]. The prevalence of urinary incontinence reaches up to 74% [3], while erectile dysfunction affects between 10% and 82% of patients [4]. This situation affects the quality of life of men [5], highlighting the need to seek effective alternatives to combat postoperative complications and sequelae.

Although physical therapy has demonstrated beneficial effects on the recovery of erectile function and urinary continence after surgical treatment for prostate cancer [6] with low-intensity shock waves, pelvic floor muscle training or electrostimulation [7], further research is needed in this field.

The high prevalence of urinary incontinence and erectile dysfunction in urological consultations has led to an increase in scientific literature in different areas of work. This has favored the publication of different bibliometric studies. Bibliometric analyses enable researchers to study, visualize, and quantify the dynamics of scientific literature within a specific field by applying mathematical and statistical methods to various dimensions of scientific research [1].

Among other authors, Ma et al. examined the worldwide tendency of erectile dysfunction research in prostate disease from papers indexed in the Web of Science [1]. Rezaee et al. evaluated documents on erectile dysfunction published in urology and sexual medicine journals indexed in MEDLINE [8]. Minto et al. conducted a bibliometric analysis of the 100 most cited articles on erectile dysfunction, as indexed in the Web of Science database [9]. Recently, Li et al. identified the side effects of prostate cancer treatment as a research focus [10].

To date, no bibliometric study has specifically examined physical therapy in post-prostatectomy recovery. Given the ongoing need for further investigation in this field, a comprehensive analysis of current scientific output is crucial to inform and guide future research directions.

For this reason, this study proposes a bibliometric analysis to identify international trends in scientific output on post-prostatectomy physical therapy, as indexed in the Web of Science database (2015–2024).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design

A retrospective descriptive study with a bibliometric approach.

2.2. Data Retrieval

The data source was the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) database within the Web of Science (WoS), widely recognized in bibliometric research [11]. This database also provides a robust statistical foundation for analyses performed with Bibliometrix in RStudio.

Bibliometrix enables both quantitative and qualitative analysis, along with data visualization tools that enhance the interpretability of results.

To minimize bias arising from database updates, all data were retrieved on a single day, 17 February 2025.

The search strategy employed in this study was structured as follows: ("prostatectomy") AND ("cancer prostat*" OR "surgery prostat*" OR "cancer") AND ("electrical stimulation" OR "musculoskeletal manipulation" OR "penile vibratory stimulator" OR "physical therapy" OR "electrostimulation" OR "neuromodulation" OR "massage*" OR "shockwave" OR "pelvic floor" OR "exercise*" OR "physical activity" OR "biofeedback" OR "hypopressiv*" OR "kegel" OR "vacuum" OR "rehabilitation") Search field: *Topic*. The reporting period covered January 1, 2015, to December 31, 2024.

Articles addressing post-prostatectomy physical therapy, published in any language, were considered eligible for inclusion. The following document types were excluded: meeting abstracts, letters, editorials, proceedings papers, early access articles, book chapters, retracted publications, drug-related studies, animal studies, and articles whose primary focus did not correspond to the scope of this review.

A total of 1,821 records were initially retrieved. Two independent reviewers evaluated the relevance of each record. Following the screening process, 1,598 records were excluded.

2.3. Tools and Data Analysis

Bibliometrix/RStudio was used to characterize, analyze, and map categories within the scientific literature [11,12].

The characterization analysis included:

a) Growth and evolution of annual and cumulative production: number of publications, annual growth rate, compliance with Price's Law, growth trends, and model fit.

b) Authors: number of contributing authors, articles per researcher, author affiliations, productivity of top authors over time, co-authorship index and rate, and productivity metrics based on Lotka's Law.

c) Authors' countries of affiliation: number of contributing countries, citation counts, international collaboration rate, and collaboration index.

d) Thematic area: word cloud analysis to identify central themes, and thematic mapping to classify topic categories.

e) WOS categories and journal dispersion according to Bradford.

The impact analysis focused on the scientific visibility of authors, countries, and publications, using citation counts and h-index metrics.

Scientific mapping techniques were employed to visualize the relational structures within the literature, encompassing co-authorship networks, international collaboration patterns, and thematic interconnections among research topics.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Evolution of production growth

A total of 228 publications were retrieved for analysis, collectively accounting for 3,211 citations. The annual scientific output exhibited fluctuations over the study period, without a consistent growth pattern, yielding an average of 22.80 ± 6.62 articles per year and an annual growth rate of 1.64%. The exponential growth model showed a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.37$, indicating a weak fit to the data (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Evolution of scientific production trend in post-prostatectomy physical therapy.

The annual volume of publications is a key indicator of the expansion and consolidation of knowledge within a given field. In this context, the observed growth dynamic is notably modest, particularly considering the rising global incidence of prostate cancer in recent years [1]. The decline in scientific output during the most recent years of the study period contributed to this weak exponential trend, falling short of the expectations outlined by Price's Law, which suggests that scientific output should double approximately every decade [13].

3.2. Authors, institutions, and co-authorships

The scientific output was generated by 1260 authors affiliated with 495 institutions. Among these contributors, 85.4% were classified as small-scale producers, having authored a single publication, while 14.6% were considered medium-scale producers, with between 2 and 9 publications. Notably, no authors met the criteria for large-scale production, defined as having published ten or more articles [see Figure 2].

Figure 2. Ratio of authors to number of documents.

These findings are consistent with Lotka's Law, which states that scientific output within a given field is disproportionately concentrated among a small number of highly prolific researchers [14]. However, despite the extensive temporal scope of the analysis, no evidence was found of such high-productivity authors in the domain of post-prostatectomy recovery, as no individual researcher had published ten or more articles on the topic. The limited number of highly productivity authors may be related to the emerging nature of the topic.

The authors with the highest number of publications and citations were P.W. Hodges (8 articles, 184 citations) and R.E. Stafford (7 articles, 169 citations), both from the University of Queensland. The remaining top 10 authors are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3 presents a three-field graph illustrating the network among the most productive researchers (left), their institutional affiliations (center), and countries of origin (right) in publications related to post-prostatectomy physical therapy. These three elements are interconnected by gray-colored links, which indicate the strength of the relationships among them. The size of each rectangle is proportional to the number of items associated with the corresponding element.

Figure 4 illustrates the temporal distribution of scientific output among the most prolific authors. The size of each bubble reflects the number of publications, with larger bubbles indicating a higher volume of articles. D. An and J.P. Mulhall demonstrated the most sustained research trajectories in the field of post-prostatectomy physical therapy. However, P.W. Hodges and R.E. Stafford achieved a higher number of publications within a shorter period.

Figure 4. Production of top authors over time.

The institutions with more than 15 publications included the University of Queensland in Australia (23 publications, 218 citations), McGill University in Canada (7 publications, 141 citations), and Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (20 publications, 220 citations) in the United States (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Most relevant affiliations

The co-authorship rate was 96.52%, with an inter-author collaboration index of 6.61 ± 4.98 .

Figure 6 illustrates the strong co-authorship connections established among the most productive contributors, with P.W. Hodges occupying a central position in the network. This centrality suggests a greater capacity to regulate the flow of information between authors within the collaborative structure.

Figure 6. Author collaboration network within the field of study.

P.W. Hodges and R.E. Stafford, whose research centers on exercise-based approaches to post-prostatectomy incontinence [15], can be regarded as key reference authors in the field, given their high publication output, citation impact, and centrality within the co-authorship network.

The University of Queensland emerges as the leading institution in research related to recovery following prostatectomy, hosting the most prolific and highly cited contributors among the publications analyzed. Researchers seeking to initiate work in this domain are encouraged to examine the studies affiliated with this institution and consider establishing collaborative partnerships to enhance scientific integration and visibility.

Institutions with the highest research output also demonstrated a higher degree of collaboration. Notably, institutional partnerships were predominantly established with organizations located within the same country (see Figure 7)

Figure 7. Institutional collaboration network in the field of study.

3.3. Geographical coverage and international collaboration

The analyzed publications involved authors affiliated with institutions in 44 countries. The leading producers were the United States (20.17%), China (17.10%), Australia (11.40%), followed by Italy and Canada (8.77%). However, the countries receiving the highest number of citations were the United States (827), Australia (605), and Canada (540) (see Table 1).

The distribution of scientific output by country reflects trends observed in other physical therapy-related topics, where the United States, China, and Australia dominate the literature [16]. These findings contrast with research on erectile dysfunction, where the leading contributors are the United States, Italy, and Canada [1]. Although the United States leads in publication volume, it does not include highly prolific authors within this field.

As seen in other bibliometric studies on prostate cancer, most of the production originates from Anglo-Saxon countries with access to financial support for research [1]. This trend can be attributed to the

fact that WoS primarily indexes journals published in English, many of which impose article processing charges that can pose significant barriers for researchers lacking sufficient funding [17]. Promoting equitable development within the field requires targeted efforts to reduce disparities between countries [1].

The international collaboration rate was 24%, with a collaboration index of 2.48 ± 0.91 , indicating a moderate level of cross-national co-authorship.

Table 1. Geographical Coverage and Collaboration Metrics of the Top 10 Producing Countries.

Country	NP (%)	TC	OutBet	OutCI	PageRank
United States	46 (20.17)	827	39.95	0.05	0.14
China	39 (17.10)	417	0	0.03	0.02
Australia	26 (11.40)	605	0	0.03	0.02
Italy	21 (9.21)	377	43.99	0.05	0.13
Canada	20 (8.77)	540	6.22	0.04	0.09
Germany	19 (8.33)	278	37.48	0.04	0.09
France	16 (7.28)	205	2.35	0.04	0.07
South Korea	14 (6.14)	193	0	0.03	0.02
Spain	14 (6.14)	163	0	0.03	0.02
Brazil	12 (5.26)	292	0	0.03	0.05

Abbreviations: NP=number of publications, TC=Total citations, OutCI= Closeness Centrality, OutBet= Betweenness centrality

Italy and the United States emerged as the most active countries in the international cooperation network, showing the highest values across all collaboration parameters (see Table 1). Notably, although Germany ranked sixth in terms of publication volume and total citations, it held the third-highest centrality in the international collaboration network, highlighting its strategic role in connecting researchers globally.

Figure 8 also illustrates the strong bilateral collaboration between the United States and Italy, as evidenced by the thickness of the connecting lines.

Despite the presence of key collaborative links, the overall density of the international research network remained relatively low, with only 24% of all possible connections established. To enhance scientific visibility and impact, future researchers should prioritize strategies that promote international partnerships. As evidenced by the findings, broader global collaboration correlates with higher citation rates and wider dissemination of research outcomes [18].

The United States and Italy occupy particularly influential positions within the international collaboration network, not only due to their substantial volume of co-authored publications and extensive interconnections with other countries, but also because of their centrality, which allows them to shape the flow and dissemination of scientific information across the network. Future research initiatives would benefit from establishing collaborative ties with authors and institutions based in these countries, as such partnerships may enhance scientific productivity and amplify the visibility and impact of research outcomes [18].

Identifying physical therapy interventions that address both conditions simultaneously could substantially enhance recovery outcomes. Among the available therapeutic approaches, Kegel exercises have shown efficacy in enhancing both urinary and sexual function [19]. However, existing studies that address these dual dysfunctions often involve poorly characterized populations, limiting the generalizability of their findings. Future research should specifically target individuals presenting with concurrent erectile dysfunction and urinary incontinence to enable more rigorous evaluation and optimization of intervention strategies.

The thematic map showed that prehabilitation and lifestyle modification were the most developed and influential themes within physiotherapy interventions (see Figure 10). Preoperative physiotherapy, particularly protocols involving aerobic activity and targeted perineal muscle training, appears to play a protective role against postoperative functional decline, with additional benefits for patients' physical resilience and psychological health [20].

In addition, physical activity emerged as a fundamental and cross-cutting theme, maintaining relevance and stability over time, and contributing to the broader development of the field. The application of electrostimulation in managing urinary incontinence represents a nascent area of investigation, currently exhibiting low conceptual density and peripheral positioning within the broader research network (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Visualization of thematic mapping.

Analysis of author-assigned keywords facilitated the identification of the principal research domains addressed in the literature [21]. In clinical settings, pelvic floor training remains the most widely implemented intervention [22], which may account for the prominence of physical activity as a thematic area exhibiting the highest conceptual cohesion and the greatest potential for sustained development within the field.

While existing studies have demonstrated the therapeutic efficacy of electrostimulation and extracorporeal shock wave therapy [23], the current evidence base remains limited. Further research is warranted to strengthen and expand this emerging area of inquiry [18].

3.5. Journal Distribution and Scientific Output

The 228 articles were published across 94 journals classified into 15 Web of Science categories. The category with the highest proportion of publications was *Urology & Nephrology* (57.23%), followed by *Andrology* (20.39%) and *Oncology* (13.15%). Although *Rehabilitation* is the category most closely aligned with the field of physical therapy, only 5.26% of the publications were found within it.

The corpus included 228 articles published in 94 peer-reviewed journals. Application of the Bradford law of scattering, as implemented through Bibliometrix, revealed a tripartite structure of journal productivity, delineating core, intermediate, and peripheral zones.

- Core: 7 journals comprising 78 articles, which collectively received 1160 citations.
- Zone 1: 22 journals with 76 articles.
- Zone 2: 65 journals with 74 articles.

The core journals with the highest number of publications and citations were *Neurourology and Urodynamics* (20 articles, 327 citations) and the *Journal of Sexual Medicine* (12 articles, 307 citations) (see Table 2). The consistent recognition of the latter as a reference journal in bibliometric studies highlights its influence and thematic relevance within the scholarly landscape [1, 8].

Table 2. Bradford Journal Core according to Bibliometrix.

Journal	NP (%)	WoS Category (Quartile)	IH	TC
<i>Neurourology and Urodynamics</i>	20 (8.77)	Urology & Nephrology (Q3)	12	327
<i>Journal of Sexual Medicine</i>	12 (5.26)	Urology & Nephrology (Q1)	8	307
<i>Translational Andrology and Urology</i>	12 (5.26)	Urology & Nephrology (Q3) Andrology (Q4) Oncology (Q2)	6	95
<i>Supportive Care in Cancer</i>	9 (3.94)	Health Care Science & Services (Q2) Rehabilitation (Q1)	5	69
<i>Urology</i>	9 (3.94)	Urology & Nephrology (Q2)	5	116
<i>BMC Urology</i>	7 (3.07)	Urology & Nephrology (Q3)	6	155
<i>International Journal of Impotence Research</i>	7 (3.07)	Urology & Nephrology (Q2)	4	91

Abbreviations: NP=number of publications, IH= H-index, TC=Total citations

The publication trajectories of the ten most productive journals can be classified into two distinct subsets (see Figure 11):

- *Neurourology and Urodynamics*, as well as the *Journal of Sexual Medicine*, commenced publication in the early stages of the study period and exhibited sustained linear growth, as evidenced by a high coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.9$).

- In contrast, the second group of journals displayed a slower rate of publication, with minimal expansion over time, indicating a more limited contribution to the longitudinal development of the field.

Figure 11. Source dynamics of the most productive journals.

In the source co-citation network, the primary cluster (depicted in red) is dominated by journals exhibiting the highest degree centrality, as reflected by the larger node sizes. These journals are predominantly affiliated with the field of urology and are recognized as the most prestigious and influential within the domain. Their strong interconnectedness through co-citation relationships underscores their central role in shaping the intellectual structure of the field.

Conversely, journals positioned at the periphery of the network—primarily from the field of oncology—display smaller node sizes, indicating lower centrality and reduced influence. Notably, no journals associated with physical therapy are present in either cluster (see Figure 12), suggesting a limited integration of physiotherapy literature into the core citation dynamics of this research area.

Figure 12. Network map of journal co-citation relationships, consisting of 25 nodes corresponding to cited journals.

Authors predominantly choose to disseminate their findings in journals specializing in urology and oncology, rather than in physical therapy-focused outlets. This trend may reflect a strategic preference for publication venues that offer greater visibility, broader readership, and higher potential for scientific impact.

Limitations

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first bibliometric analysis specifically focused on physical therapy interventions following prostatectomy. The study included original research articles and review papers published between 2015 and 2024, indexed in the WoS. Although these inclusion criteria help ensure scientific quality, they may also limit the comprehensiveness of the field’s representation. The exclusion of grey literature, such as letters to the editor, conference abstracts, and other non-peer-reviewed sources, may have introduced citation bias, given that these sources are also subject to academic referencing [1].

To enhance the breadth and representativeness of future analyses, additional international databases such as Scopus and PubMed should be considered. Furthermore, the configuration of analytical parameters within Bibliometrix—particularly those used to construct bibliometric maps—can significantly influence the results. Careful selection and transparent reporting of these parameters are essential to ensure methodological rigor, reproducibility, and comparability across studies.

4. Conclusions

This bibliometric study provides an up-to-date overview of scientific publications on physical therapy in the post-prostatectomy context between 2015 and 2024. The results show that although the volume of publications has increased only slightly and is unevenly distributed, this line of research has progressively consolidated its presence in the scientific literature. The output is concentrated primarily among a few authors, institutions, and countries, highlighting that international collaboration remains moderate and that there is clear room to expand research networks.

Furthermore, the thematic analysis reveals that erectile dysfunction and pelvic floor muscle training remain the predominant areas of focus, while other physical therapy interventions, such as electrostimulation or shockwave therapy, represent emerging areas that require further development. Taken together, these findings suggest the need to strengthen collaborative research, diversify lines of study, and expand the participation of physical therapy specialists to consolidate the available evidence and enhance the scientific impact in this field.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, C.T.P.; methodology, C.T.P., L.B., and L.S.; validation, C.T.P., L.B., and L.S.; formal analysis, C.T.P.; investigation, C.T.P.; writing—original draft preparation, C.T.P.; writing—review and editing, C.T.P., L.B., and L.S.; visualization, C.T.P., L.B., and L.S.; supervision, C.T.P., L.B., and L.S.; project administration, C.T.P., L.B., and L.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: Not applicable.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

IH	H-index
NP	number of publications
OutBet	Betweenness centrality
OutCl	Closeness Centrality
TC	Total citations
WoS	Web of Science

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